

ANALYSIS OF THE APPLICATION OF HYBRID MATERIAL ON A SILL

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ABSTRACT

The car body is composed as a shell construction and contains many parts which have different targets. One of these parts is the sill, which will be discussed in this paper.

The sill is not only a load-bearing element. The stiffness of the sill ensures the safety of the vehicle occupants in case of an accident. Moreover, with focus on electric vehicles, further specific characteristics of the sill must be taken into account. The protection of the battery, which can be positioned between two sills, is very important, because in case of a car accident a possible intrusion of the sill into the battery would be very dangerous.

This article discusses the possibilities and characters of using hybrid material on a sill aiming to increase the stiffness and to decrease the weight. In general, hybrid materials are a composite of different materials. In this work, the hybrid material consists of a type of metal and some kind of composite material.

Furthermore, using hybrid material for the sill has several further benefits. A light body has many potential benefits, increased safety, and better environmental performance. To assume using of new hybrid materials, it is necessary to specify the conditional boundaries of a these materials, which will also be subject of this paper.

There are two primary research questions which guide this paper, and they are formulated as follows: What kind of materials could be used to optimize stress behavior of the sill and its form? It is also necessary to assess the individual capabilities of the composite materials more specifically, product costs, and energy absorption. To evaluate the correct combination of the parameters, it is necessary to ensure a methodological approach. This paper will introduce a method to identify what load cases and what combinations of parameters make sense to investigate.

1 INTRODUCTION

This article discusses the possibilities and characters of using hybrid material on a sill. Of course, a sill is just an example for using hybrid material; in other words, for finding of a combination of some kind of metal and some kind of composite material. The traditional structure of a sill is a shell design or profile construction design and is produced from a sheet steel. This makes the designing much easier because the material is homogeneous and isotropic. The designers are already familiar with this “simple” elastic and plastic behaviour of a material or structure. The reason why we are trying to use another kind of material or combinations of materials with behaviour that is more complicated is that the potential of composite material is really high. Not only does the weight make a decision for that,

but also is the ratio of the mass and energy absorption important. This is in composite material approximately three or four times higher [14].

The reason why a sill has been chosen here is that a sill is not only a load/bearing element. The sill is a very important body part in case of a side crash [19]. That is why a high stiffness is required. The vision of using hybrid material in this case is the improvement of “ratio of weight/stiffness” in case of a crash, in other words, passive safety.

The passive safety is one really important factor for the occupants. That means that the car body should prevent their injury in the crash case. In our case, the side crash is major. In order to understand how important passive safety is to the occupants regarding side crashes, some information concerning this topic is provided. The chest and pelvis are the regions of the body that are most likely to be injured in side impacts [20], and are probably the result of a limited stroke punch crush of the door, as described by [18, 3]. [20] confirmed, on the basis of NASS data, that the predominant injurious contact in pelvic and chest injuries is the side interior surface, especially the door [23].

Nowadays, it is also important to consider the passive safety with regard to battery in the bottom of the car of electric vehicle [19]. The protection of the battery is very important, because in case of a car accident a possible intrusion of the sill into the battery would be very dangerous and the battery might explode.

To validate and simulate these cases of crash some input dates are necessary. The European New Car Assessment Program (EuroNCAP) was chosen to provide the important force and geometry dates. EuroNCAP form the basis of the structural requirements of the sill in the event of a crash. The EuroNCAP program is the result of an evolution of Crashworthiness Rating System for Cars (CWRSC), taken place in 1997. The CWRSC, and the EuroNCAP as well, were founded by the British transport research facility Transport Research Labotory (TRL). Both of these programs are to evaluate the safety potential of motor vehicles [17]. The CWRSC will not be discussed in this article. The NCAP program assesses and reviews the passive safety of new vehicles and publishes the results for both consumers and producers. The measures to improve passive safety is reducing the consequences of accidents, not accident-avoiding. The program uses additional security requirements of the legislature. As a result, the carmaker's reviews EuroNCAP should be taken into account for a list of requirements for vehicles [17].

After finding the essential boundary conditions it is necessary to take into account the geometry of the sill and the materials used. Two different types of skirts have to be distinguished. Firstly, there is the profile and the shell construction [2]. In the shell construction sheets can be connected by riveting, welding or gluing. The shells refer to all the stresses and are self-supporting. Profiles produced by extrusion, transform torsional and bend stresses into tensile and compressive forces [13]. In this article the shell construction of a sill will be discussed. In addition to the shell construction, other potential structures for improvement of stiffness will be presented [16]. As for the materials used, several components are combined in the composite construction by means of a permanent connection with each other constructively in order to achieve desired material properties. Examples for this would be strength, stiffness, corrosion resistance, and wear resistance. Examples of such design various car parts can be used. One of these is a demonstrator of a VW Polo lightweight door. A weight saving of over 50% was achieved compared to the original steel door by using a hybrid material composite of CFK and magnesium here. An advantage of the hybrid construction next to the high potential for lightweight construction is the possibility of achieving an optimum utilization of the material properties and a positive addition to these properties. The disadvantages are: the high production cost caused by the joint connection, the fail criteria, which partially limited assessment of the component behaviour, and the possible risk of corrosion at the contact points [12, 21, 4, 22].

2 NCAP TESTS

In this article, not all NCAP crash tests will be considered, because as for our purposes, only some of them are relevant. Below, the side impact with barrier and pole will be illustrated. The frontal impact is not going to be discussed in this context because in that given case, mainly the front parts of the body are deformed while the sill remains virtually unaffected. [11]. The sill is obviously one of the

parts in which the frontal collision force is divided. But this value is negligible at speeds in NCAP tests.

2.1 Side barrier impact

Figure 1 shows the situation and conditions of the NCAP side barrier impact. In the side impact test, a wheeled cart with deformable barrier drives at the speed of 50 ± 1 km/h against the driver's side of the test vehicle. The center of the barrier is aligned with the target impact point. This point is 250mm behind the "R Point". The position of this point is replaced by the manufacturer. The lower side of the barrier has a height of 300mm [17, 9, 6]. If the boundary conditions of this test are known, it is then known that the height of the impact depends on the structure of the body. As for a small vehicles, this means that the sill will not be hit directly. However, as for higher vehicles, the sill will hit directly.

Figure 1: Side barrier impact [17]

Mobile Deformable Barrier Advanced European (AE-MDB) is used for side crash tests according to the rules of the UNECE. Figure 2 shows the structure of the AE-MDB. Due to changing of stiffness of the fronts of modern cars, a new concept was developed. EuroNCAP developed the AE-MDB, and continued to work with the industry and is going to use this in the future. The full weight of the mobile frame with a front-mounted part is 1300 ± 20 kg. The cover story of the trolley is located 1000 ± 30 mm behind the front axle longitudinal center 500 ± 30 mm above the ground. [6, 9].

Figure 2: Mobile deformable barrier [6]

2.2 Side pole impact

Figure 3 shows the situation and conditions of the NCAP side pole impact. In this case, the car is traveling on a wheeled carriage with $29 \pm 0,5$ km/h against a vertical standing pole with the diameter of 254 ± 3 mm. The car laterally meets with the driver's side on this obstacle. The pillar is a metal structure that starts at the collision side maximum 102mm above the lowest point of the tire and extends at least 100mm above the highest point of the roof. The impact of the vertical reference line of the middle column is the intersection between the outer lateral surfaces of the vehicle with a vertical plane passing through the center of the crash dummy head. This plane is oriented at an angle of 75° to the center line of the wagon in the longitudinal direction. The crash occurs on the driver's side [17, 10, 8]. In this case, all the affected parts of the car that were found in the plane of poles will be hit directly.

Figure 3: Side pole impact [10, 17]

3 FRAME DESIGN

The car frame structure should be introduced to describe the dimensions of the problem first. Figure 4 shows an example of a simplified frame of the car which should be continuously used to obtain other necessary information such as the position of the sill or values of forces in the connecting areas – in other words, the reactionary forces. To determine the sill height it is necessary to know the type of the car body and ride height. It is therefore taken into account that this body size is approximately that of a Golf VI. In this case, the ride height is 89mm [5].

Figure 4: Frame design of a car, CATIA

Electric vehicles play an increasingly important role in passive safety. The battery location in the chassis is a very important factor which will not be discussed in detail in this article. What is important for obtaining significant boundary conditions is the allowable deformation value of the sill. This value can simply be evaluated as the distance from the battery sill. Figure 5 shows a simple representation of this issue. This is, of course, a general question, because each manufacturer or brand uses different sizes of battery and its location. This is only a very simplified representation of what we take into account in the design or sill stress evaluation. This issue continues to be extended by crossbeams and their location. The crossbeam allows a more drastic reduction of distortion of the sill by loading.

Figure 6 shows a very simplified representation of a static situation, which is supported by five places. The load is of course different for both types of crash tests. One of the tasks of the sill is to initiate the energy into the floor structure and divide [7].

Figure 5: Bottom view of the frame design, CATIA

Figure 6: Bottom view of the frame design

In the side pole impact the sill is hit directly. The largest intrusion is produced there. The pole hit the B-pillar and the sill at the same time, from where most of the energy is directed into the floor structure. Figure 7 shows a possible load path of the side pole impact. It does not show an electric vehicle, but a standard vehicle where we can discover a seat cross beam.

The opposite case is the side barrier impact, where the sill is only a reaction of the B - pillar. By this point, the sill is pushed to the inside of the car. In both cases, it is necessary to assess the impact stiffness which plays a very important role.

Figure 7: Load path of the side pole impact [11]

METHODS

Finding a methodological approach to give a useful combination of property of isotropic and anisotropic materials, its location in a defined load can be very difficult. In this case is not going about a classical load, but about crash. Furthermore, it is very important to identify suitable combinations of the shaping part that greatly affects the result. All these factors must be sensibly included in the methods, which uses a combination of composite materials and iron. This combination should be used for the sill. The program PAM-Crash is used for the calculation of crash characteristics.

A method that addresses similar issues is topology optimization. Topology optimization is a FEM method in which a space, such as a square, bearings points, and force application points are defined. The program should then find the ideal structure.

This article focuses on selected types of steel and composite materials. Among the frequently used steel in the automotive industry includes light Alloy, for example aluminum, to weight reduction. Among these different kinds of aluminum alloy are included. Table 1 shows the properties of different

aluminum alloys. Regarding the composite material, this methodological approach addresses glass fiber, carbon fiber and polymer fiber. Table 2 shows the properties of different kinds of fibers [15, 24].

	Unit	EN AW-AL 99,5	EN AW-AL Mg3	EN AW-Al Zn5Mg3Cu
<i>Min. tensile strength</i>	MPa	75	190	450
<i>Yield point</i>	MPa	20	80	370

Table 1: Properties of different kinds of aluminum alloy [16]

	Unit	Glass fiber	Carbon fiber			Polymer fiber
		E	HT	HMS	HM	AF
<i>Diameter</i>	µm	3-25	7,0-8,0	5,0-7,0	6,5	12
<i>Thermal expansion</i>	10 ⁻⁶ /K	5,1	-0,46	-0,46	-1,08	-2
<i>Density</i>	g/cm ³	2,6	1,75	1,78	1,79	1,44
<i>Tensile strength</i>	MPa	3400	~3000	3900	~2500	~3000
<i>stiffness</i>	MPa	73000	228000	230000	350000	65000-130000

Table 2: Properties of different kinds of fibers [15, 24]

Because of the great complexity of the task, the methodological approach must be proceeded step by step and only the case of side pole impact has to be considered. Also, the connection between these different materials cannot be taken into account, because it would clearly exceed the scope of this article.

Therefore, the simplified model which has been described in figure 6 is a very important point. A 160x130x1750mm rectangular section will serve as a very simplified structure, which is supported at four points, but in different planes. In this case, the B-pillar was neglected, because the exact behavior of the resistance and geometry are not known. Figure 8 shows the simple model, which consists of only 6 layers of CFK in the direction of 0°, 30°, 60°, 90°, 0° and 30° related to the length direction of the sill. The final thickness of the wall is 3mm. In this case HMS from table 2 was taken into account, because of very high tensile strength 3900MPa. The properties of the used composite materials (matrix and fiber) for simulation are shown in table 3 [1]. These are actually not the parameters that were useful for PAM-Crash, because this program needs the parameter of both matrix and fiber separately and calculate the combination by itself.

This simple profile, which shows the usually used size of the profile of the sill, is loaded on the pole crash impact. The impact speed by these tests is 29km/h, the pole weight is 300kg, approximately a quarter car, because the force is spread over the sill, roof, door structure and B-pillar. This article is not going to deal with the exact values, but it is going to compare the behavior of the deformations caused by different forms and material combinations.

	Tensile Modulus E ₁ (GPa)	Tensile Modulus E ₂ (GPa)	Shear Modulus G12 (GPa)	Poisson's Ratio (ν12)	Fiber volume friction (%)
<i>T300 Carbon/5208 Epoxy</i>	1,8103	1,0276	7,1724	0.28	70

Table 3: Properties of the used composite material in the sill [1]

Figure 8: Simply model of 6 layers of T300 Carbon/ 5208 Epoxy, 3mm wall thickness, PAM-Crash

In reality as well as in the side pole impact tests, the car is moving and crashing towards the pole. When working with a simple model of the sill, it is much more complicated to specify the boundary conditions of the sill. Because of that the game will be turned. The sill will not move, as it did before, but the sill will be crashed by the pole instead.

Figure 8 shows a simplified model of the sill with a profile size of 160x130mm. This space should not be exceeded now and the optimal geometry should be found. The stiffness of the profile is likely to be influenced by different material descriptions and different profile geometries. In figure 9, some other kinds of geometry are shown, which will, being composite material, also be taken into account; their stiffness, or, in other words, deformations, will be proven. As for this direction of the load, the stiffness must be ensured in the movement direction (y-direction). If the profile lost its whole width, in our case 160mm, this would mean a big disadvantage. Of course, the first one, a rectangle, is the simplest. This case has already been discussed in figure 8. The deformation of the profile is 28mm in the given circumstances. As previously stated, deformation can only be traced in the inner edge of the profile due to avoidance of contact with the battery. Figure 10 shows the impact test of the rounded rectangle profile. The difference between the simple profile and the rounded rectangle is really small. However, it is quite noticeable that in figure 8, the maximum deformation occurs at the outer right corner.

Figure 9: Different basic geometry/rectangle (a), rounded rectangle (b), ellipse (c), hexagonal (d)

Figure 10: Deformation of rounded rectangle of 6 layers, 3mm wall thickness, PAM-Crash

From this representation we can observe that the deformation that is important for our purposes is reduced very slightly, but the profile is completely crushed. In Figure 11 we can see the simulation results of the next two profiles.

Figure 11: Deformation of ellipse and hexagonal chart of 6 layers, 3mm wall thickness, PAM-Crash

It is illustrative that of all of these simulations an ellipse is the appropriate profile. Here, the deformation measured was around 200mm, which is the highest one of all the given opportunities. Conversely, we can observe that a rounded rectangle profile has the smallest deformation; here, the deformation is 27mm. In this case, the profile in cross section is completely distorted.

Since this article deals with the comparison or combination of different types of materials and shapes of profiles, it is necessary to examine the behavior of identical profile in case of a crash, defined as alloy. Table 1 shows some of the properties of lightweight alloy and its basic strength values. Nowadays, the usage of lightweight material is absolutely common in automotive design. Wrought aluminum alloys can partially achieve both very high tensile strength R_m and high yield $R_{p0.2}$. Ductility is a classic feature of the light metal. Due to this, it is possible to produce complex shapes of aluminum. In our case, high strength combined with low weight is required. It is very important to opt for the right material. Table 1 lists three types of material that are commonly used in the industry. Due to our boundary conditions the strongest one will be selected, namely EN AW-Al Zn5Mg3Cu. Values required for simulation are given in Table 4. The Poisson's Ratio for Aluminum alloy is roughly 0.33.

	Modulus of elasticity(GPa)	Min. tensile strength (GPa)	Yield point (GPa)
EN AW-Al Zn5Mg3Cu	72	0.45	0.37

Table 4: Properties of EN AW-Al Zn5Mg3Cu [16]

This kind of material will also be used on a simple profile with 160x130mm. The simulation of impact test has the same boundary conditions as before. Figure 12 shows the model of this steel profile. In this case, the deformation is 48mm, which means that it is a little higher than some of the composite profiles. The material and production costs are not as high here.

Now, the deformations of individual types of profiles with composite material and simple rectangle aluminum alloy profile are known. Our current motivation is to create a meaningful combination of these two materials and their shape. One good combination seems to be the rounded rectangle of composite material and the rectangle of aluminum. If these profiles were joined simply, they would reach a weight of 13,7kg. A meaningful combination should be found to achieve a sufficient rigidity with less weight. Figure 13 shows a profile as a combination of aluminum alloy and composite material (Carbon/Epoxy), or, in other words, hybrid material.

Figure 12: Deformation of rectangle lightweight alloy profile, 3mm wall thickness, PAM-Crash

Here, the structure is built of three layers of composite material and 1,5mm sheet steel (*EN AW-Al Zn5Mg3Cu*). Each layer reaches a thickness of 0,5mm of composite material. The total wall thickness of both reaches 3mm. This combination of material is connected by welding: two rows of welds, 35 in each side on the top of the profile; one row, 35 welding points in the bottom row of the profile. By this combination a shell structure as common in practice could be reached. The total weight of the hybrid structure is 6,8kg.

Figure 13: The structure of the hybrid profile, 3mm wall thickness

Figure 14: Deformation of the hybrid lightweight steel profile, 3mm wall thickness, PAM-Crash

4 CONCLUSION

This article deals with passive vehicle safety in the sill, and, more precisely, with the structure and usage of hybrid materials for this area with a view on how to improve the ratio of deformation and weight. The sill is loaded by stress tests mainly on side impact. Because of the possibility to verify which of these two principles is more serious and important for validation, this article deals with the side pole impact. As thoroughly described in section 3, a substructure of electric vehicle was included here. It was necessary to ensure maximum deformation of the inner sill area of the vehicle frame. In the event of a collision, the inner edge of the sill could crash into the battery and the battery might explode. Due to the great complexity of the model and the problems, the sill has been simplified to a simplified beam profile of different materials. First, it was possible to verify which kind of profile type is suitable for high loads. A rounded profile shows the smallest result of deformation. This profile was defined as a carbon/epoxy material and its weight is just 5kg. Furthermore, the simplified modeled alloy structure, which was defined as EN AW-Al Zn5Mg3Cu, was examined. In this simulation, it was possible to verify that the structure's weight is 43% higher than it is in the case of the rounded profile of composite material; it also shows a worse deformation of 44%. The aim of this article was to find a suitable combination of materials to achieve greater rigidity with less weight. Figure 13 shows the combination of two structures with different materials. Here, composite material was used, carbon and epoxy, and EN AW-Al Zn5Mg3Cu. The weight of the hybrid structure is higher by 26% than it is in the case of the simply composite rounded profile. However, it is lower by 22% than alloy structure is. This combination of materials was then welded by weld-points. Figure 14 shows the resulting deformation of hybrid structure which achieved less deformation which is lower by 2% than in the case of alloy structure. This ratio is worse than that of carbon fiber structure. Nevertheless, it is important to realize that the price of carbon is many times higher than that of steel. In conclusion, we can say that the deformation remained essentially the same with lower weight by 22%. In this case, it is conceivable that the hybrid materials and the proper use of their properties have a great future with regard to specific deformations.

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